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A TOOL TO ENSURE CONSTRUCTIVE ALIGNMENT IN COURSE DESIGN

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WORKSHOP

According to the principles of constructive alignment first described in the literature by Tyler (1949) and later on by Biggs (1999), an outcome-based curriculum should be designed as a coherent system containing three central elements: learning outcomes, teaching strategies and assessment strategies.

Through our experience of teaching support, we have noticed that integrating content and contextual elements (e.g., the resources available, the audience, etc.) allows the teacher to focus on his/her immediate concern (i.e., designing a course) without disconnecting it from the realities of higher education. Overall course alignment helps both students and teachers to reach learning outcomes.

We have developed the course design canvas (CDC) to support teachers throughout their course design process. The canvas builds on the constructive alignment theory and extends it by adding the content and contextual elements. It can be used both for creating or revisiting a course as well as for reflecting on its overall alignment.

The canvas was developed to address course design for both engineering and non-engineering education. To make the session as relevant as possible, the tool will be presented with an example in the field of engineering.

The workshop proposes to introduce participants to the course design canvas. Participants will familiarize themselves with the tool and process by applying it to a course of their choice. To do so, they will work with an electronic version of the canvas using Mural. As part of the workshop, participants will be invited to share

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their canvas with a peer. The workshop will end with a group debrief and a short Q&A session.

In terms of learning outcomes, participants will be able to:

- Describe the elements of the course design canvas
- Apply the canvas to a course of their choice
- Reflect on their canvas through peer-work

The organizers will share with the participants comments pertaining to the alignment of the different canvas produced and, more generally, a set of best practices.

Participants will be also able to export their canvas for further use.

TAKEAWAYS FROM WORKSHOP

- The canvas makes the “alignment” part clear but less the “constructive” part
- One could benefit from a way to integrate students who do not have the same level into the canvas and how to include this in the “teaching strategy”
- The meaning of curriculum (as part of the context) could be made clearer
- How can one ensure coherence at the course level or at the program level

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